

IMPROVING THE CUSTOMER SERVICE SYSTEM IN HOTELS

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Abstract. *In this article, we will consider hotel and hotel service forms, types of service and the possibilities of improving, upgrading and developing their system.*

Keywords: *hotel, hotel types, hotel forms, service, service types, service system.*

The Specific Features of Hotel Services in the Hospitality Industry

The specific feature of hotel services in the hospitality industry is the process where employees of the enterprise temporarily accommodate clients for their stay and provide them with services.

Hotel services can be conditionally divided into two categories:

Mandatory Service Package: These are the main products and services included in the price of staying in a room. After the contract is concluded, the consumer is provided with standard mandatory services.

Additional Services: Hotel guests pay separately for these services (e.g., room cleaning, dry cleaning, sauna, barber, massage services, parking, billiards, and others).

The essence of accommodation services is to provide clients not only with specialized buildings but also with mandatory and additional services. The hotel product includes the work and services provided by the employees of the establishment. For example, the doorman receives guests and handles registration, room attendants clean the rooms, the receptionist greets and guides the guests, and so on.

The organization of hotel services in hotels is determined by the goals and needs of the clients. In every hotel, clients can be offered completely different categories of rooms. The differences between these rooms may include area, location, furniture, equipment, and others. However, every hotel room, regardless of its category, must have the following equipment:

Bed

Table and chairs

Armchair or sofa

Wardrobe for clothes

Lighting systems

Trash bin, and others.

Additionally, each room must have information about the hotel, and an evacuation plan in case of fire or emergency must be posted in a visible place.

Food Services

Hospitality involves carrying out other economic activities, with food being an inseparable part of it. In some hotels, guests can have access to a restaurant where they can enjoy a cup of coffee or a meal. The general catering facility in the hotel can be an independent enterprise or part of the hotel, operating as one of its divisions. The classification of restaurants depends on the service level and the type of dining services offered to the visiting guests.

Luxury restaurants stand out due to their elegant and exquisite interior design and furnishings, the level of comfort for spending time, high-quality service systems, a wide variety of

gourmet and special dishes for ordering, various drinks and cocktails, live music, and other services. First-class establishments cater to guests by offering harmony, comfort, luxury, and well-being, along with innovative dishes, products, new types of drinks, and complex cocktails, all in line with a delightful and guest-welcoming menu.

Safety: Every restaurant must undergo certification according to the announced class and must be accredited by the relevant state authorities responsible for standardization and metrology. Various types of catering establishments have different requirements based on necessary standards, but all of them share the responsibility for ensuring the safety of visitors' lives and health, the environment, and the security and well-being of the clients' property.

Additional Services

In addition to accommodation and food services, it is advisable to introduce additional services in hotels. These services improve the service system and ensure greater customer satisfaction. These services include concierge services, additional sports services, cleaning services, room service, barber services, and others. These services are an important component of providing a good and enjoyable stay and a meaningful experience while spending time at the hotel.

The best variant of service is offering high-level service to guests during their arrival and departure. Hotel staff welcomes the guest, assists with bringing the luggage to the room, helps with check-in, or parks the car in the parking lot. When guests are leaving, the staff takes their luggage and belongings to the car. This means hotel staff can serve dozens or even hundreds of guests per day. The characteristics of hotel services are diverse, and they can serve multiple functions — although these services can vary significantly based on standards and regulations, they are offered at hotels of various categories.

In modern and luxurious hotels, the general service staff may provide innovative services to hotel guests in other ways. Hotel staff may provide services such as receiving late arrivals and registering them, organizing light dinners, making phone calls at a specific time, or calling a taxi, available around the clock. Hotel staff is also responsible for the cleanliness of public areas and ensures the safety of the guests' stay in the hotel. Upon request, staff may deliver messages, provide transfers, and more.

Hotel staff often organizes various recreational activities, including visits to cinemas and theaters, excursions, guided tours, car rentals, poolside bars, restaurants, barbershop and massage services, wellness services, and other services. Most hotel establishments have an information board at the reception to help new arrivals with useful information.

State Service

The list of additional services depends on the hotel's category or level. As for household services, not all hotels are equipped to offer these. The organization of household services should be planned carefully and thoroughly. These services are typically available in accessible areas, and their schedule should be posted at the reception.

Household services include:

Urgent washing or cleaning of clothes and other items

Repair and ironing of personal items

Dry cleaning

Shoe repair or cleaning

Storage of items, valuables, and luggage

Safe rental

Room service

Rental of additional dishes, equipment, furniture, household appliances (dishes, irons, televisions, sports equipment, etc.)

It is recommended to familiarize yourself with the most requested hotel services by guests, their characteristics when choosing a hotel, organizing tours to sightseeing spots, and obtaining translation services. Additionally, the purchase and reservation of tickets for entertainment events, car rentals, and restaurant bookings should be arranged by contacting hotel staff when necessary.

9 Tips for Improving Customer Service in the Hotel Industry

One of the key factors for the success of opening and managing a hotel is customer service.

Tip 1: Send an Email Before the Guests Arrive. Sending an email, message, or pre-arrival contact before the guests arrive can significantly improve customer service in hospitality. Additionally, it can simplify the check-in process.

Tip 2: First Impressions Matter a Lot. The biggest mistake in welcoming guests is treating them poorly as if you're doing them a favor. This can negatively impact their entire stay.

Start with a warm greeting and a smile, and let the warmth of your hotel be felt. Remember, at the end of the day, they are not just numbers, but people who should feel welcomed. Therefore, it is important to be friendly.

Tip 3: Create Easily Accessible Communication Channels. Communication is a key part of enhancing guest experience and customer service in hospitality. Your ability to meet your guests' needs speaks volumes about your hotel.

In large hotels or those with older clientele, phone lines are often preferred. If your hotel is large and the Wi-Fi coverage isn't ideal, phone lines still work well. For smaller hotels or those with younger, more tech-savvy guests, quick channels like WhatsApp, chats, and other messaging apps are a great option to respond promptly and effectively.

Tip 4: Provide Valuable Information for Your Guests. One of the traditional sources in hotels is the welcome book, which usually provides information about the hotel and its facilities. However, nowadays, many hotels have moved away from such books.

Today, creating video tutorials, e-books, or sharing content via social media is a great alternative.

Tip 5: Treat Guests Like People, Not Numbers. One of the most common mistakes is treating people as mere numbers, not as individuals. Guests coming to your hotel are not machines that pay you money; they are living, breathing people who deserve beautiful treatment.

Tip 6: Availability of Wi-Fi. Believe it or not, Wi-Fi availability plays a crucial role in guest service in today's hotels. Think about how you feel when you go somewhere without access to the internet.

Tip 7: Celebrate Special Occasions. One of the most effective ways to improve customer service and enhance the guest experience is by celebrating special occasions. What do we mean by this? Simply put, celebrate special events for your guests and your hotel.

For example, if a group of people orders a reservation to celebrate a birthday at your hotel, why not surprise them with a birthday cake? Or if your guests are celebrating an anniversary, offer them a flower or a bottle of wine!

The same applies to your hotel. For example, if your hotel is celebrating its anniversary, celebrate it! Surprise your guests with gifts, dynamic activities, events, or anything that shows them they are part of a larger family.

Tip 8: Monitor Customer Reviews. Another highly effective way to improve customer service in the hospitality industry is by monitoring customer reviews.

Guest feedback, both positive and negative, helps you draw clearer conclusions about the performance of your hotel. By doing so, you can take actions that truly impact the quality of service at your hotel.

Tip 9: Consult with Experts. The final method for improving customer service in hospitality is consulting experts, such as those at IHCS! This allows you to review and analyze your hotel to find opportunities for improvement. It will help you execute every action precisely, use resources efficiently, and achieve clear results!

In addition to improving service, hotels should also think about creating new innovative projects to enhance the customer service system. Many guests refer to online reviews before making a reservation, so it is crucial for hospitality companies to maintain high ratings by providing excellent service and offering innovative new features to guests. Studies show that potential guests are 40% more likely to book a hotel based on its online reputation. Therefore, it is essential for hotel owners to ensure that all their guests are satisfied with their stay and that they provide impeccable mandatory and additional services.

Hotels need to improve their service potential, surprise guests with new innovative ideas and updates, and know how to engage them to ensure they leave the hotel satisfied and with a good impression.

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